

HEALTH PROBLEMS OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS PARTICIPANTS

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Abstract. *In this article says about topical issues of pedagogy - ensuring the health of students at different stages of the system of continuous education in the context of its reform.*

Keywords: *preschoolers, pupils of schools and secondary educational institutions, students, health, health-saving technologies.*

As you know, the main functions of persons engaged in pedagogical activities in the system of continuous education are educational, educational, developmental, health-saving activities and preparation for the coming life (social, family, professional). In this regard, the leadership of Uzbekistan pays great attention to the issues of health protection of the younger generation in the context of educational activities in educational institutions of the republic, which is one of the important factors in improving the quality of education at all stages of the lifelong education system. This is evidenced by the proclamation of 2023 - "The Year of Human Care and the Quality of Education" [1]. According to the Great Medical Encyclopedia, the concept of health includes the following: "Health is the state of the human body when the functions of all organs and systems are balanced with the external environment and there are no painful changes" [2].

In the pedagogical dictionary, the reference book notes that health is characterized not only qualitatively, but also quantitatively; there is a concept of the degree of health, determined by the breadth of the adaptive capabilities of the body. And although health is opposed to disease, it can be associated with it by various transitional states [3, 205 p.]. These transitional states occur in the case of the beginning of education, at one stage or another of the system of continuous education, which may be accompanied by a violation and even loss of the physical, mental or spiritual health of the younger generation, caused by the corresponding influence of various environmental factors, as well as a result of non-compliance with the requirements of interpersonal mental hygiene relationships or education and upbringing.

At the present stage of development of society, researchers have accumulated extensive experience in developing theoretical and methodological foundations for designing a health-preserving educational environment in preschool educational institutions, secondary schools, secondary specialized vocational educational institutions (academic lyceums and professional colleges), higher educational institutions on the use of health saving technologies in the educational process, on the problems of the relationship between health and training loads in the educational process, psychological and pedagogical support of the health-preserving activities of the subjects of the educational process [4].

Currently, there are more than 1,000 general education schools, about 5,000 pre-school educational organizations, about 1,000 organizations of secondary vocational education systems and over 150 public and private higher educational institutions in the republic. The given data testify that a large part of the children's and youth population is covered by educational institutions and every teacher who implements educational work must carry it out in such a way as not to "harm" and "not damage" the health of pupils.

An analysis of the literature data indicates that human health mainly depends on factors such as:

- heredity, tendency to hereditary diseases;
- social environment and lifestyle in it;
- ecological and climatic conditions;
- age-related changes [5].

Knowing and taking into account the impact of these factors on the health of students is an integral element of the health-saving activity of a teacher. At the same time, it should be remembered that the impact of the above factors on human health is ambiguous: 20% depends on hereditary factors, 20% - on the environmental conditions of the environment, 10% - on the activities of the healthcare system, the remaining 50% depends on the way of life [6].

The beginning of the first educational environment (preschool educational organization) dictates the need to take into account the peculiarities of the process of adaptation of the child to the new conditions of his life, in which his individuality, interests and inclinations should be manifested, various competencies should develop, including in such areas of development as physical development and healthy Lifestyle.

In particular, a child of 6-7 years old:

- shows physical activity in accordance with their capabilities and possible norms of physical development;
- is able to perform various types of motor activity in a coordinated and purposeful manner;
- uses fine motor skills in various life and educational situations;
- regulates its movements with the help of the senses;
- applies personal hygiene skills;
- knows the basics of a healthy lifestyle and nutrition;
- follows the rules of the basics of life safety [7].

At the same time, a child who has not developed an arbitrary regulation of his behavior experiences great difficulties in adapting to the requirements of a preschool educational institution, which leads to nervous overstrain and a breakdown.

The next stage, associated with entering school, may be accompanied by the so-called "school stress" and in some cases lead to a violation of various types of health of students of a somatic, physical, mental and moral nature.

Our pupils have shown that the duration of the working day of modern schoolchildren (taking into account homework, attending sections, circles, extra classes, etc.) approaches 12 hours, and for high school students - 14-16 hours. Naturally, all this negatively affects the health of students and possible ways to solve this problem are:

- increasing the number of physical education lessons (at least 3 hours per week);
- changing the content of physical education lessons (each lesson should become a new path to health);
- use between lessons of small forms of physical activity of students (physical education minutes, physical breaks, etc.);
- conducting special physical education classes for children with disabilities;
- correction of pedagogical technologies that contribute to the formation of hypodynamia and muscle clamps in schoolchildren (interaction between physical education teachers and subject teachers);

- providing schoolchildren with the opportunity to exercise in the gym and on sports grounds outside school hours.

The solution of these problems can be safely considered as health-creating technologies that complement educational technologies for preserving and strengthening the health of schoolchildren [8].

At the stage of secondary vocational education, which includes primary school of vocational education, vocational colleges and technical schools, students acquire the skills of a particular profession and at the same time are called upon to acquire knowledge about the safety precautions of the corresponding profession in order to prevent the possibility of certain injuries and violations of one or another other kind of health.

Education in universities is due to the fact that future professionals, especially those who acquire pedagogical specialties, must first of all learn how to maintain their health, since the profession of a teacher is associated with great mental and emotional stress and take care of maintaining the health of their future pupils and students who we have to live in the conditions of reforming education, introducing digitalization of education, active use of modern information technologies and innovative learning. In the context of the above, graduates of higher educational organizations are the future economic, labor, defense and cultural potential of the state, and society is vitally interested in ensuring that this generation is physically, mentally and spiritually healthy and protected from the effects of various health-destroying factors. The fact is that, according to researchers, more than 20% of students have two or three chronic diseases at once (respiration, digestion, urogenital area), a high level of tuberculosis, viral hepatitis, and intestinal infections. At the same time, about 80% of students smoke, over 70% drink alcohol, and up to 17% have already tasted drugs. All this in general leads to an increase in the number of diseases, an increase in the number of deaths, impaired physical development and a reduction in average life expectancy (9).

Due to the urgency of the problem of preserving the health of students, special, health-saving, technologies in education are currently being developed. Their classification was developed, which included

- technologies that provide hygienically optimal conditions for learning;
- psychological and pedagogical technologies used by teachers in classroom and extracurricular activities;
- technologies for teaching a healthy lifestyle;
- corrective technologies.

In particular, technologies for teaching a healthy lifestyle include:

- physical education classes;
- problem-playing (game trainings and game therapy);
- communication games;
- classes from the series "Health";
- self-massage and acupressure, etc. [10].

Thus, it should be noted that in all educational organizations, medical and pedagogical teams should conduct systematic and purposeful work to ensure the health of students, which will bring up a harmoniously developed, healthy generation.

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